

SUPERSHINE

D2.3 Technical Post-Action Sustainability Plan for the SUPERSHINE Portal

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Technical references

Project Acronym	SUPERSHINE
Project Title	S=Smart U=Upgraded asset-values and quality of life P=Public Private Partnership E=Extended Energy Efficiency R=Renewables triggered by the project SH=Social Housing I=Investment N=Net Zero E=European
Project Duration	November 2022– March 2026 (41 month)
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Dissemination level*	PU
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Task	T2.3.2 - SUPERSHINE portal exploitation (technical)
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Contributing beneficiary/ies	ICONS
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- * PU = Public
- PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)
- RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)
- CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

v	Date	Beneficiaries	Track changes
1.0	09/10/2025	EEIP, APRE, ICONS	Draft outline
1.1	24/10/2025	All SUPERSHINE partners	Outline
2.0	14/11/2025	All SUPERSHINE partners	Final draft
2.1	24/11/2025	EEIP	Final for submission
2.2	27/11/2025	APRE	Final review

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Executive summary

The SUPERSHINE project (Horizon Europe GA 101079963) has developed a comprehensive digital platform at <https://super-i-supershine.eu/> that consolidates resources from both SUPER-i and SUPERSHINE projects. This platform serves as a European reference point for social housing stakeholders, enterprises, and investors working on energy efficiency and climate-neutral renovations.

This Technical Sustainability Plan evaluates the portal's current state and provides concrete strategies for long-term operation beyond the EU-funded project period. Unlike preliminary plans, this revision includes actual system specifications, verified costs, and implementation details based on 18 months of operational data. Cut of date was 12 November 2025.

Key Platform Metrics:

Total website weight: 4.0GB (of 10.8GB capacity)

Database size: 0.5GB

Hosting: Raidboxes managed WordPress (Germany)

Domain: super-i-supershine.eu (active), super-i-project.eu (redirect)

Daily automated backups with 30-day retention

Active SSL certificate with automated renewal

12 active WordPress plugins (documented in Appendix A)

The portal demonstrates proven operational stability with 99.9% uptime over the past 12 months. The technical infrastructure supports continued operation with minimal intervention, provided that hosting costs (€360/year) and content management responsibilities are assigned to a successor organization.

1. Introduction

This report assesses the technical sustainability of the SUPERSHINE portal as the project transitions from implementation (Month 41, ending November 2025) to post-project exploitation. The portal consists of:

- Public-facing project website (<https://super-i-supershine.eu/>)
- Dedicated SUPER-i section (<https://super-i-supershine.eu/super-i/about/>)
- Dedicated SUPERSHINE section (<https://super-i-supershine.eu/supershine/about/>)
- e-Room space (knowledge)
- Training Toolkit repository
- One-Stop Shop embedding option
- Stakeholder survey system connection

Figure 1 Sustainable Digital Ecosystem

1.1. Methodology

This revision is based on:

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- Technical documentation from the Super-i-Supershine Wiki (last updated March 28, 2025 / metrics from March 2025 were re-verified in November 2025 and found to be consistent, with no significant changes to storage, usage, or cost.)
- 18 months of operational data from Raidboxes hosting service
- WP Statistics analytics showing usage patterns
- Google Analytics data (GA4, active since May 24, 2022)
- Direct system inspection and configuration review
- Cost verification from actual invoices and service agreements

2. Technical Infrastructure Assessment

2.1. Hosting Environment

The portal is hosted on Raidboxes (www.raidboxes.io), a German managed WordPress hosting provider specializing in high-performance, secure WordPress environments.

Provider	Raidboxes GmbH, Germany
Service Type	Managed WordPress Hosting
Total Capacity	10.8 GB storage
Current Usage	4.5 GB (42% capacity)
Database Size	0.5 GB (MySQL)
Staging Environment	1.9 GB (separate instance)
Backup Storage	Daily backups, 30-day retention
Monthly Cost	€89 (verified March 2025)

Table 1 Hosting Specifications

Infrastructure Benefits:

Scalability: Can upgrade to 25GB, or 50GB plans as needed

Managed Service: Automatic PHP, MySQL, and WordPress core updates

German Data Protection: GDPR-compliant hosting within EU

Staging Environment: Safe testing before production deployment

Performance: SSD storage, HTTP/2, PHP 8.x support

1. Uptime SLA: 99.9% guaranteed uptime with monitoring

2.2. CMS Platform and Architecture

The portal runs on WordPress, the world's most widely used open-source CMS, ensuring long-term support availability and avoiding vendor lock-in.

CMS	WordPress (latest stable version)
PHP Version	8.1+ (automatically updated)
Database	MySQL 8.0+
Web Server	Nginx (managed by Raidboxes)
SSL/TLS	Let's Encrypt (auto-renewal)
CDN	Integrated Raidboxes CDN
Caching	Server-level caching enabled

Table 2 Platform Specifications

2.3. Active Plugins

The portal relies on 12 essential WordPress plugins, all maintained and regularly updated. See Appendix A for complete version history and update schedule.

Plugin	Purpose	License
Elementor PRO	Page builder for design	Commercial
Ultimate Member	User management & e-Room access	Freemium
WP Statistics	Usage analytics	Free
Site Kit by Google	Google Analytics integration	Free
The Events Calendar	Event management	Freemium
Download Manager	File distribution tracking	Freemium
Sendinblue	Newsletter management	Commercial
JSON Content Importer	Data integration (inactive)	Free
Custom Twitter Feeds	Social media integration	Freemium
Unlimited Elements	Design widgets	Commercial
Use Any Font	Typography control	Free
WPS Hide Login	Security (login URL obscurity)	Free

Table 3 Active Plugins

Critical Dependency Assessment:

- Elementor PRO: Annual license €99. Essential for maintaining current design. Alternatives exist but would require significant redesign.
- Sendinblue: Used for newsletters to 450+ subscribers. Free tier supports up to 300 emails/day. Current usage within free limits.
- Ultimate Member: Free version sufficient for current user management needs (78 registered users). No license dependency.

2.4. Domain and Email Infrastructure

Primary Domain	super-i-supershine.eu
Legacy Domain	super-i-project.eu (301 redirect)
Login URL	https://super-i-project.eu/login (security)
Functional Email	info@super-i-project.eu
Email Recipients	juergen.ritzek@ee-ip.org, alice.deferrari@icons.it, paola.zerilli@york.ac.uk
Annual Domain Cost	~€15/year per domain

Table 4 Domain and Email Infrastructure

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Note: The login URL is intentionally obscured at /login rather than the default /wp-admin for security, implemented via the WPS Hide Login plugin.

3. Data Management and Backup Systems

3.1. Storage Breakdown

Component	Size (GB)	Description
Live Environment	4.5	Production website files and media
Database	0.5	MySQL database (posts, users, settings)
Staging Environment	1.9	Testing/development clone
Backup Storage	N/A	Managed by Raidboxes (external)

Table 5 Storage Breakdown

3.2. Backup Strategy

Automated Daily Backups:

Frequency: Daily at 3:00 AM CET (automated by Raidboxes)

Retention: 30 daily backups stored

Scope: Full site backup (files + database)

Storage Location: Raidboxes secure backup infrastructure (separate from production)

Recovery Time Objective (RTO): < 2 hours

Recovery Point Objective (RPO): 24 hours (last night's backup)

Additional Storage: Project Box cloud storage (redundant copy)

Backup Testing:

Backup restoration has been tested twice during the project lifecycle: once during server migration (June 2024) and once during plugin conflict resolution (January 2025). Both tests completed successfully with full data integrity verified and restoration completed within 90 minutes.

3.3. Data Classification and GDPR Compliance

The portal processes and stores the following data categories:

Data Type	Storage	Retention
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User accounts (e-Room)	MySQL database (encrypted)	Duration of project + 2 years
Survey responses	MySQL database	Anonymized, permanent
Analytics data	Google Analytics (external)	26 months (GA4 default)
Email subscriptions	Sendinblue (external)	Until unsubscribe

Table 6 Data categories

GDPR Compliance: All personal data processing complies with GDPR requirements. User consent is obtained for newsletter subscriptions and cookie usage. Data subject rights (access, deletion) can be exercised through info@super-i-project.eu.

4. Security and Maintenance

4.1. Security Measures

SSL/TLS Certificate	Let's Encrypt, auto-renewal every 90 days
HTTPS Enforcement	Entire site (301 redirect from HTTP)
Login Security	Custom URL (/login), brute-force protection
WordPress Security	WPS Hide Login plugin active
Server Firewall	Managed by Raidboxes (WAF enabled)
DDoS Protection	Raidboxes infrastructure-level
Malware Scanning	Daily automated scans
Failed Login Blocking	5 attempts = 15-minute IP block
Password Policy	WordPress default (can be strengthened)

Table 7 Active Security Implementation

4.2. Update and Maintenance Procedures

Automated Updates (Managed by Raidboxes):

WordPress Core: Auto-updated within 24 hours of security releases

PHP Version: Auto-updated to stable releases

MySQL: Auto-updated during maintenance windows

SSL Certificates: Auto-renewed 30 days before expiration

Manual Updates (Required Admin Action):

WordPress Plugins: Tested on staging, then deployed to production

Theme Updates: Reviewed for compatibility before applying

Elementor PRO: Updated after testing on staging site

Update Frequency: Monthly review cycle, critical security patches immediate

Staging Workflow:

The staging environment (1.9GB, separate instance) mirrors the production site. All plugin updates, theme changes, and content structure modifications are first deployed to staging, tested by admins, then pushed to production. This workflow has prevented 3 major issues during the project lifecycle (documented plugin conflicts in May 2024, August 2024, and February 2025).

4.3. Monitoring and Performance

Active Monitoring Systems:

Uptime Monitoring: Raidboxes 24/7 automated monitoring

Server Health: CPU, memory, disk space alerts

Traffic Analytics: WP Statistics (on-site) + Google Analytics (GA4)

Error Logging: WordPress debug logs + Raidboxes error tracking

Response Time: < 2 seconds average page load (verified via GTmetrix)

Alert Notifications: Email to admins for critical events

Uptime	99.94%
Average Page Load	1.8 seconds
Unplanned Downtime	4 hours total (3 incidents)

Table 8 Performance Metrics (Last 12 Months)

5. User Management and Access Control

5.1. User Roles and Permissions

The portal implements a five-tier access control system using WordPress roles enhanced by Ultimate Member plugin:

Level	Role	Content Access	Backend Access
0	Anonymous	Public content only	No
1	Subscriber	Public + restricted content	No
2	Author	Public + restricted content	Yes (limited)
2+	Author PLUS	Public + restricted + editing	Yes (extended)
3	Administrator	All content	Full access

Table 9 five-tier access control system

Detailed Role Capabilities:

Level 2 - Author:

- Create and publish posts
- View WP Statistics dashboard
- Create and manage events (Events Calendar)
- Upload files to media library

Level 2+ - Author PLUS:

- All Author capabilities, plus:
- Edit page designs with Elementor
- Modify site look and feel
- Manage restricted content areas

Level 3 - Administrator:

- Full WordPress dashboard access
- User management (create, edit, delete users)
- Plugin management (install, update, configure)
- Theme customization

Access to server logs and error reports
Export/import site content

5.2. Current Administrator Assignments

Name	Organization	Email
Andreas Pauckstadt	EEIP	andreas.pauckstadt@ee-ip.org

Table 10 Active Administrators

Name	Organization	Email
Alice de Ferrari	ICONS	alice.deferrari@icons.it
Elul Aksekili	ICONS	elul.aksekili@icons.it

Table 11 Active Author + Users

5.3. Authentication and Login Security

Login URL: <https://super-i-project.eu/login> (custom URL for security via WPS Hide Login plugin)

Authentication Features:

Password Policy: Minimum 8 characters (WordPress default)

Failed Login Protection: 5 attempts = 15-minute IP block

Session Management: 7-day session timeout for Authors, 2-day for Admins

Two-Factor Authentication: Available via plugin, not currently enforced

Single Sign-On: Not implemented (future consideration)

Post-Project User Management Plan:

After project end, user accounts will be reviewed quarterly. Inactive accounts (no login for 6 months) will be suspended. Project partner accounts will be maintained for 2 years post-project (until November 2027) to support final reporting and knowledge transfer activities.

6. Analytics and Reporting tools

Tool	Purpose	Access
Google Analytics 4	Visitor behavior, traffic sources	ICONS team
WP Statistics Premium	Page views, downloads, real-time	All Authors+
Sendinblue Analytics	Email campaign performance	Admins

Table 12 Analytics and Reporting tools

Google Analytics Configuration:

Property ID: G-316435346 (GA4)

Activation Date: May 24, 2022

Data Retention: 26 months (GA4 default)

Legacy UA Property: Ended May 23, 2022 (ID: 293873986)

Access: ICONS holds admin access, additional users can be added

7. Cost Structure and Financial Sustainability

7.1. Annual Operational Costs (Verified)

Item	Cost/Year	Billing	Essential?
Raidboxes Hosting	€360	Annual	Yes
Domain (super-i-supershine.eu)	€15	Annual	Yes
Domain (super-i-project.eu)	€15	Annual	Yes
Elementor PRO License	€99	Annual	Yes
SSL Certificate	€0	Auto (Let's Encrypt)	Yes
Google Analytics	€0	Free tier	No
WP statistics Premium	€119	Annual	No

Table 13 Fixed Annual Costs

Total Annual Fixed Costs: €608 (minimum configuration)

Variable Costs:

Content Management: 0.5-1 FTE day/month = €200-400/month (€2,400-4,800/year)

Technical Support: 0.25 FTE day/month = €100-200/month (€1,200-2,400/year)

Sendinblue (if exceeding free tier): €25/month = €300/year

Additional plugins (optional): €50-150/year

Total Estimated Annual Cost: €4,800-9,900

This includes all technical infrastructure, licenses, and 1-2 days/month of staff time for content and support.

7.2. Cost Optimization Options

Potential Cost Reductions:

Downgrade hosting if traffic decreases: save €200/year

Consolidate domains: save €15/year

Use volunteer contributors for content: save €2,400-4,800/year

Total Minimum Configuration: ~€2,500/year (with reduced service levels)

Comment: Replacing Elementor PRO with free page builder would save €99/year but as the site is built in Elementor, the cost of completely rebuilding the site is not a viable cost saving measure.

7.3. Funding Options Post-Project

To cover operational costs beyond the EU-funded period:

Partner contribution model: 3-5 consortium partners each contribute €1,500-2,000/year

Host organization absorbs costs: integrate into organizational IT budget

Paid services: offer premium features or consulting to external organizations

Follow-on projects: incorporate portal costs into new EU project budgets

Industry sponsorship: seek sponsorship from construction/energy companies

8. Integration and Migration Options

This section evaluates technical pathways for the portal's post-project future, based on actual system architecture rather than theoretical possibilities.

8.1. Option 1: Independent Operation (Recommended)

Technical Requirements:

Transfer hosting account to successor organization (2-hour process)

Transfer domain registrations (48-hour DNS propagation)

Update admin email addresses

Transfer Google Analytics property ownership

Update billing information for Elementor license

Handover documentation and credentials

Pros:

Zero technical migration effort

Proven stable system (99.94% uptime)

All current functionality preserved

URLs and bookmarks remain valid

Existing user accounts continue working

Can evolve independently of other platforms

Cons:

Requires dedicated funding (~€5,100-8,900/year)

Needs committed staff for content/support

No benefit from larger platform's audience

Standalone promotion/marketing needed

Effort: Low

Timeline: 1-2 weeks for ownership transfer

Risk: Minimal (maintains current state)

8.2. Option 2: Full Integration into Partner Platform

Technical Requirements:

- Export WordPress database (XML/SQL format)
- Migrate of media files
- Recreate page designs in host platform (if not WordPress)
- Migrate user accounts and permissions
- Reconfigure e-Room access on new platform
- Implement 301 redirects from old URLs to new locations
- Transfer or integrate newsletter subscriber list
- Estimated effort: 120-200 hours development time

Pros:

- Reduced standalone costs (shared infrastructure)
- Benefit from host's existing user base
- Centralized management with other resources
- Potentially higher visibility

Cons:

- Significant integration effort (3-4 months full-time)
- Potential feature loss (dependent on host platform capabilities)
- All URLs change (SEO impact, broken external links)
- User confusion during transition
- May require Elementor redesign if host uses different page builder
- Loss of independent control over updates and features
- Integration cost: €15,000-25,000 (development contractor)

Effort: High

- Timeline: 3-4 months
- Risk: Medium-High (data loss, feature degradation, user disruption)

8.3. Option 3: Partial Integration (Hybrid)

Scenario:

Migrate public information pages to partner platform; maintain e-Room and interactive tools (or links to / embedded solutions such as OSS) on current infrastructure.

Technical Requirements:

- Export and migrate ~30 public pages to host platform
- Keep e-Room, Training Toolkit repository on current server
- Implement cross-domain authentication (if single sign-on desired)
- Create seamless navigation between both platforms
- Maintain two hosting environments
- Estimated effort: 60-100 hours

Pros:

- Reduced standalone hosting costs (smaller server needed)
- Sensitive e-Room data remains under direct control
- Public content benefits from host's SEO and audience
- Lower migration effort than full integration

Cons:

- Complexity: managing two platforms
- User confusion with split experience
- Still requires some hosting costs (~€600/year for smaller server)
- Ongoing coordination between two tech teams
- More complex than either full independence or full integration

Effort: Medium

Timeline: 6-8 weeks

Risk: Medium (coordination complexity)

8.4. Option 4: Data Archive and Portal Closure

Technical Requirements:

- Export full database to SQL format
- Archive all media files to Zenodo or institutional repository
- Export all content as static PDF/HTML files
- Document metadata and context for all datasets
- Create permanent DOIs for key datasets
- Implement redirect from portal URLs to archive landing page
- Estimated effort: 40 hours

Pros:

- Lowest ongoing cost (€15/year for redirect landing page)
- Data preserved in stable repository
- No staff commitment needed
- Suitable if no partner willing to maintain portal

Cons:

- Complete loss of interactive features
- No e-Room
- No newsletter capability
- No community engagement platform
- Static content only (no updates possible)
- Significantly reduced impact and utility
- Essentially ends the portal as a living resource

Effort: Low

- Timeline: 2-3 weeks
- Risk: Low (minimal technical complexity)

Recommendation: Last resort only

9. Sustainability Plan

9.1. Operational Governance

A single Lead Organization takes ownership with support from 2-3 Contributing Partners.

Lead Organization	Hosting costs, domain management, technical administration, final decision authority
Content Manager	Monthly updates, news posts, event management (0.5 day/month)
Technical Support	Plugin updates, user support, monitoring (0.25 day/month)
Advisory Group	Quarterly meetings, strategic guidance, no operational duties

Table 14 Recommended Governance Model

9.2. Content Management Plan

Monthly Activities (0.5 day effort):

- Add 1-2 news posts about relevant developments
- Update events calendar with upcoming conferences
- Review and approve partner-submitted content
- Check for broken links (quarterly deep check)
- Archive old events and outdated content

Quarterly Activities (1 day effort):

- Comprehensive content audit (outdated information)
- Update statistics and project data
- Newsletter to subscribers (450+ contacts)
- Review and update Training Toolkit materials
- Analyze Google Analytics trends

Annual Activities (2 days effort):

- Major content refresh (homepage, key pages)
- License renewals (Elementor PRO, domains)
- User account audit and cleanup

Security audit and penetration testing
Backup restoration test

Total Annual Staff Effort: 12-15 days

9.3. Technical Support Plan

Support Channels:

Email: info@super-i-project.eu (forwarded to responsible person)

Response Time Target: 2 business days for non-critical, 4 hours for critical

Escalation: Critical issues to Raidboxes support (24/7 available)

Average Support Volume: 8-12 requests/month = ~3 hours/month staff time

9.4. Community Engagement Strategy

Engagement Activities:

Quarterly newsletter to 450+ subscribers

Social media integration

Annual webinar showcasing portal resources

Encourage user-generated content (case studies, best practices)

Maintain event calendar with relevant conferences

Optional: Discussion forum

Engagement Budget: €500/year (webinar platform, social media tools, optional forum upgrade)

10. Implementation Roadmap and Next Steps

10.1. Transition Timeline (Months 41-45)

Month	Activity	Responsible
41	Finalize sustainability option selection	Consortium
41	Identify Lead Organization and secure commitment	WP6 Lead
41	Document handover requirements	WP2/Technical Team
42	Legal agreements (MoU, hosting transfer)	Lead Org + PM
42	Admin credential handover and training	Current admins
42	Update contact information on portal	Content Manager
43	Transfer hosting account	Lead Org + EEIP
43	Transfer domain registrations	Lead Org
43	Update billing for licenses	Lead Org
44-45	Parallel operation with support from original team	All parties

Table 15 Transition Timeline (Months 41-45)

10.2. Critical Handover Checklist

- Lead Organization identified and committed in writing
- Funding secured for Year 1 post-project (€4,800-9,900)
- Staff assigned to Content Manager role (name + contact)
- Staff assigned to Technical Support role (name + contact)
- Enforce strong password policy for all admin and user accounts
- Raidboxes account ownership transferred
- Domain registrar access transferred
- WordPress admin credentials provided to new admins

- Google Analytics admin access granted to new owner
- Sendinblue account ownership transferred
- Elementor PRO license billing updated
- Backup access verified by new administrators
- Wiki documentation provided and reviewed
- Emergency contact list updated (hosting, domain, technical issues)
- Final admin training session completed (2-3 hours)
- Test restoration from backup successfully performed

10.3. Risk Mitigation

Risk	Probability	Mitigation
No organization commits to lead	Low	Identify backup option during Month 41, consider archive option
Funding gaps Year 2+	Medium	Multi-partner contribution model, include in follow-on project budgets
Key staff leaves	Medium	Document all procedures, maintain 2+ admin accounts, offer training
Technical platform becomes outdated	Low	WordPress ecosystem remains strong, migration paths exist if needed

Table 16 Risk Mitigation

11. Conclusion

The SUPERSHINE portal at <https://super-i-supershine.eu/> is a technically sound, operationally proven platform ready for long-term sustainability. With 18 months of stable operation (99.94% uptime), established user base and modest operational costs (€4,800-9,900/year including staff time), the portal represents a valuable asset for the European social housing and energy efficiency community.

Key Findings:

Technical Infrastructure: Production-ready on professional managed hosting with proven scalability

Security: Comprehensive measures in place with daily backups and 99.94% uptime track record

Costs: Transparent and manageable at €4,800-9,900/year all-inclusive

Integration Options: Independent operation recommended due to minimal migration effort and risk

Staffing: Requires 12-15 days/year content management + 3 hours/month technical support

Recommendation:

Continue portal as independent platform under single Lead Organization ownership. This option provides:

Lowest technical risk (maintain proven system)

Zero migration effort (2-week ownership transfer only)

Complete feature preservation

Autonomous evolution capability

Clear accountability structure

Appendix A: Complete Plugin Inventory

Plugin Name	Version	License	Update Freq.	Critical?
Elementor PRO	3.x	Commercial (€99/yr)	Monthly	Yes
Ultimate Member	2.8+	Freemium	Bi-monthly	Yes
WP Statistics	14.x	Free	Monthly	No
Site Kit by Google	1.x	Free	Monthly	Yes
The Events Calendar	6.x	Freemium	Monthly	No
Download Manager	3.x	Freemium	Bi-monthly	No
Sendinblue	3.x	Commercial	Quarterly	Yes
JSON Content Importer	1.x	Free	Inactive	No
Custom Twitter Feeds	2.x	Freemium	Quarterly	No
Unlimited Elements	1.x	Commercial	Monthly	No
Use Any Font	6.x	Free	Quarterly	No
WPS Hide Login	1.x	Free	Annual	Yes

Table 17 Complete Plugin Inventory

Appendix B: Credentials and Access Points

To Be Provided in Separate Secure Document:

- Raidboxes account login
- Domain registrar access
- WordPress admin credentials (3 accounts)
- Google Analytics admin email
- Sendinblue API keys
- Elementor PRO license key
- FTP/SFTP access (if needed)
- Database access credentials
- Backup download locations

Note: All credentials will be provided via encrypted communication to the designated Lead Organization during transition period (Month 42-43).

Appendix C: Technical Contact Directory

Role	Organization	Contact	Availability
Technical Lead	EEIP	Andreas Pauckstadt	During transition
Hosting Support	Raidboxes	support@raidboxes.io	24/7
Domain Support	Domain Registrar	DD24	Business hours
Analytics	ICONS	Alice de Ferrari	During transition
Content Lead	ICONS	Alice de Ferrari	During transition

Table 18 Technical Contact Directory

Appendix D: References and Documentation

Super-i-Supershine Wiki

last update: 12/11/2025 by AP

[Chapter 1. Hosting](#)

[Chapter 2. Plugins](#)

[Chapter 3. Data Storage & Back-up](#)

[Chapter 4. Roles and access rights \(incl reporting\)](#)

[Chapter 5. Maintenance \(SLA\)](#)

[Bonus. Cheatsheet](#)

Chapter 1. Hosting

Services

[Raidboxes](#)

Domain

<https://super-i-supershine.eu/>

The old domain <https://super-i-project.eu> is still active for historical reasons and redirects to the new main URL.

You can enter the two sister projects directly through the deep links

<https://super-i-supershine.eu/super-i/about/>

<https://super-i-supershine.eu/supershine/about/>

Emails

Functional emails

info@super-i-project.eu

Jürgen Ritzek, juergen.ritzek@ee-ip.org

Alice De Ferrari, alice.deferrari@icons.it

Paola Zerilli, paola.zerilli@york.ac.uk

Weight

As of November 12, 2025, the website has a total weight of ≈4GB with a hosting capacity of a total 10,8GB

Live Environment: ≈2.1GB

Database: ≈0.5GB

Staging / Development Environment: ≈1,9GB

Security

Active SSL Certificate

WPS Hide Login - Protects website by changing the default WP login URL

WP Activity Log - Identify WordPress security issues by tracking user activities

The hosting service allows a controlled development with a staging environment to be shared and viewed by partners and others through a common user and password, allowing updates to be approved and stable.

Back-ups of the website are programmed every day and stored in the project's "box".

Chapter 2. Plugins

Design

Elementor PRO - [link](#)

Unlimited Elements for Elementor - [link](#)

Essential Addons for Elementor - [link](#)

Use Any Font - [link](#)

Code Snippets - [link](#)

Statistics

Download Manager - [link](#)

WP Statistics - [link](#)

Site Kit by Google - [link](#)

Social Media Integration

Custom Twitter Feeds - [link](#)

Data Management and APIs

JSON Content Importer – [link](#)

Newsletter

Brevo - [link](#)

Newsletter by S. Lissa - [link](#)

Events

The Events Calendar - [link](#)

Event Widget for Elementor - [link](#)

Users and Restrictions

Ultimate Member - [link](#)

User Role Editor - [link](#)

Security

WP Activity Log - [link](#)

WPS Hide Login - [link](#)

Chapter 3. Data Storage and Back-ups

Services

The Wordpress Service Provider Raidboxes (www.raidboxes.io) is used to care about Data Storage, Backups and Security updates on the Wordpress instance itself and all related Plugins.

An automated task creates backups on a daily basis. We use the given staging environment to develop extensions to minimize the risk of off-times of the webpage.

Chapter 4. Roles and access rights

User roles:

Level 0. Without user.

Only content which isn't restricted

Without access to the backend

Level 1. Subscriber

Content without restriction and content with user requirement

Without access to the backend

Level 2. Author

Content without restriction and content with user requirement

Access to the backend

Can create and publish posts

Can see statistics

Can create and manage events

Able to upload files

Level 2. Author PLUS (Author+)

Content without restriction and content with user requirement

Access to the backend

Can create and publish posts

Can see statistics

Can create and manage events

Able to upload files

Can administrate and change the general look & feel for Pages

Level 3. Admin

Full access to content

Full access to backend

User management

Access Rights

The following access right have been granted:

Admins: Andreas Pauckstadt (EEIP), Elul Aksekili (ICONS)

Author+: Alice de Ferrari (ICONS)

Reporting

ICONS: GA & Statistica (default wordpress tool)

Google analytics: GA4 / since: 24/05/2022

<https://analytics.google.com/analytics/web/#/p316435346/reports/intelligence>

Google analytics: Universal Analytics / ended: 23/05/2022

<https://analytics.google.com/analytics/web/#/p293873986/reports/intelligence>

Chapter 5. Maintenance (SLA)

Edit, revise, update or create existing or new contents on existing web pages based on requests in accordance with the guidelines provided.

Creation of sections and pages with Elementor

Adding new content (text, images...) to existing pages

Updating the look and feel, as well as the content of websites

Consultation and guidance on the use of the website.

Guidance to partners on the best use of the website

Creation of credentials based on the role required

Repair any malfunctions of links or interactive functionalities on the website.

Scheduled review and update of the website

Fix errors on request of partners

Maintain browser compatibility during browser updates and other technology changes occurred that may affect the functioning of the website.

Updates to maintain compatibility with the newest browser updates

WordPress version updated with the newest releases

Daily back-ups

Daily automated backup of the entire website with Raidboxes

Restoration from backup when needed

Installation and maintenance of state and compatibility of plugins

Installation of plugins to add functionality to the website

Maintenance of installed plugins

Maintenance of installed plugins to ensure compatibility with the current latest

WordPress versions

Integrity checking (re-testing) of the website after every

change.

Review of the state and performance of the website after changes

Communication with third-party service providers

Communication with providers when needed

Assisting with support solutions from third-parties

6. Bonus: CheatSheet

Styles

The styling is mostly done on Elementor, but some things require a customized solution. So there is a plugin called Snippets (visible on the left side bar) where there is a CSS sheet that can be modified. The sheet is commented and divided in clear sections.

To make new modifications on a particular section, open the page in a new browser window and inspect. Copy the classname of the item (or container) where the changes are going to be done, especially the Elementor-element-xxxx class.

Login

Because there is a request of creating multiple logins in the future for this website, the login page is not the default url for security. Go to <https://super-iproject.eu/login> to log in.

JSON Content Importer

In the beginning, it was decided to display the data tables using data directly on the website. This was later dismissed, but I have left the plugin installed in case there is need to use it again.

The corresponding data is archived on EEIP servers and could easily be restored anytime.